

Forecasting Green Investments and Generation of Green Energy in India

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ABSTRACT

Investment activities which focus on projects that are committed to production of alternative energy sources, conservation of natural resources and implementation of clean air and water projects are called 'Green investments'. It is the investment necessary to reduce air and greenhouse gas pollutant emissions without reducing the production and consumption of non-energy goods significantly. Thus those projects which are environment friendly are called green projects. Investment in these projects is called green investment. It is also known as Socially Responsible Investment (SRI). Renewable energy plays an important role in the augmentation of grid power, providing energy access, reducing the consumption of fossil fuels and low carbon development. The government of India has undertaken several policy measures in the last five years such as guidelines for procurement of solar and wind power, infrastructure status for solar projects. Hence the researcher decided to study the growth in green investment in India leading to more production of green energy. The research is done based on secondary data available on websites and global reports available. Investment in renewable energy in India and across the world is increasing and so is the production. The study aims to see the correlation between the investments and production of renewable energy. Using the predictive model of regression, forecasts are made. The correlation co-efficient indicates a strong relation between the investments and production of green energy in India.

Keywords: - Green Investment, Socially Responsible Investment (SRI), Renewable energy, Green energy

I. Introduction

Investment activities which focus on projects that are committed to production of alternative energy sources, conservation of natural resources and implementation of clean air and water projects are called Green investments. It is the investment necessary to reduce air and greenhouse gas pollutant emissions without reducing the production and consumption of non-energy goods significantly. Thus those projects which are environment friendly are called green projects. Investment in these projects is called green investment. It is also known as Socially Responsible Investment (SRI). This study aims at forecasting investments into green energy and forecasting the production of green energy in India. It also studies the correlation between the investments and generation of green energy in India.

The research is done based on secondary data available on websites and reports. The data is obtained from Renewables Global Status Reports 2019. Investment in renewable energy in India and across the world is increasing and so is the production. The study aims at knowing the effect of increase in investment on production of renewable energy in India.

India is very ambitious in promoting renewable energy. Renewable energy plays an important role in the augmentation of grid power, providing energy access, reducing the consumption of fossil fuels and low carbon development. The government of India has undertaken several policy measures in the last five years such as guidelines for procurement of solar and wind power, infrastructure status for solar projects. Hence the researcher decided to study the growth in green energy and green investments.

II. Research Objectives

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To forecast the investment in green energy in India
2. To forecast the generation of green energy in India
3. To find the effect of green investments on the production of green energy in India

III. Research Methodology

This study aims at forecasting the investment done in green energy and the production of green energy. The paper also aims to find the effect of green investments on the production of green energy. Data has been collected for a period of 10 years since 2008 for various energy sectors such as solar power, wind power, bio power, bio fuels and hydro power from Renewables Global Status Reports. This data has been analyzed to find out the growth in green investments and green energy. We have analyzed the growth in various energy sectors using statistical tools such as predictive analysis for regression and correlation co-efficient. We have also relied on basic time series comparisons for visualization purposes.

IV. Literature Review

Priyanka Goel (2016) in her paper on green Finance cites that India has great potential to raise green finance by creating awareness among corporate. She has mentioned the green financial products and services in India such as green bonds, insurance and loan schemes for green energy. Green banking practices of leading public and private sector banks have been explained in the paper. Keerthi B.S.(2013) has studied the challenges and opportunities on green finance. Attractive green finance indices are explained in the paper. Various financial products for environmental upgradation and few green projects are specified. Gudimetla (2011) has listed companies which are

involved in green investing. He has mentioned the projects for which these companies have invested funds. He has further mentioned green projects in India and green funds in India. In the article “Green Finance: Fostering sustainable development in India” Babita Jha & Priti Bakhshi (2019) have analysed the trends in green financing in India and examined various challenges in green financing. They have detailed the major loans extended by financial institutions towards green projects.

V. Renewable Energy

Research and Development efforts by Government of India in renewable energy continue to make advances in making technologies affordable and sturdy with assured quality. Revolution in the power sector is driving rapid change towards renewable energy future. While momentum in the power sector is positive, all countries need to deliver the emissions reductions demanded by the Paris climate agreement or the aspirations of the Sustainable Development Goal 7. China, Europe and United States account for nearly 75% of the global investment in renewable power and fuels. Corporate sourcing of renewable power is also on the rise.

Decentralised solutions, grassroots efforts, start-ups, off-grid applications, innovation, solar, thermal and other activities are not visible when reporting at the global level, yet they collectively make a significant contribution. These developments offer opportunities for scaling up and furthering the transition in the energy system. The electricity transition is well under way, due to increase in installed capacity and cost competitiveness of solar and wind power.

Investments in Renewable Energy

Global Investment in renewable energy has reached 288.9 billion US\$ in 2019. Global investment in renewable has increased even as costs continue to fall, and developing and emerging countries extended their lead over developed countries. Investment was focused on solar energy which secured US\$ 139.7 billion in 2018. The investment in China was the highest. The next largest investments were in US, Japan and India. Solar power and wind power continue to dominate the sector. The various sources of investments are asset finance, corporate and government R & D, public market investment, venture capital and private equity.

Chart 1

Source: Renewables Global Status Report 2019

Table 1: Forecasted Green Investment in India (Billion US\$)

Year	Investment	Lower Confidence Bound (95%)	Upper Confidence Bound (95%)
2008	5.3		
2009	4.2		
2010	8.6		
2011	13		
2012	6.7		
2013	4.9		
2014	7		
2015	8.8		
2016	14.8		
2017	18.3		
2018	15.4		
2019	16.9 F	10.5	23.4
2020	18.0F	11.6	24.4
2021	19.0 F	12.6	25.5
2022	20.1 F	13.7	26.6
2023	21.1 F	14.8	27.6

Forecasted using linear regression

The predictive model of linear regression is used to forecast the investments in green energy in India for the years 2019 to 2023. The analysis shows that investments will be increasing every year. Confidence level of 95% is kept. Investment is a dependent variable. Chart 2 is prepared from the data in Table 1.

Chart 2

Forecasted using Linear Regression

Table 2: Renewable Energy Generation in GWh in India

Source	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Hydro Power	137504	129953	129986	132190	143743	165336
Solar Power	7749	9450	13086	26871	39268	50103
Wind Power	29414	29704	46018	52666	62036	64639
Bio mass	15944	17631	14659	15682	16325	13843
Other	414	420	433	564	425	366
Total Renewable Power	191025	187158	204182	227973	261797	294287
Total Utility Power	1105446	1168359	1236392	1302904	1371517	1385114
% Renewable Power	17.28	16.02	16.51	17.50	19.09	21.25

Source: All India Renewable Energy Generation by CEA

From Table 2 it is evident that the production of renewable energy in India constitutes 21.25% in 2019 whereas in 2014 it was 17.28% of the total power generation. Thus there is 4% increase. Chart 3 depicts the data given in Table 2.

Chart 3

Chart 3 shows the information given in Table 2. It can be seen that hydro power is generated more than any other source of renewable energy. Solar and wind power generation is also increasing every year since 2014.

Table 3: Forecasted Green Energy in India (in GWh)

Year	Power Generated	Lower Confidence Bound (95%)	Upper Confidence Bound (95%)
2014	191025		
2015	187158		
2016	204182		
2017	227973		
2018	261797		
2019	294288		
2020	317034F	291123F	342946F
2021	340759F	305881F	375637F
2022	364484F	322499F	406469F
2023	388209F	340144F	436273F

Forecasted using Linear Regression

The predictive model of linear regression is used to forecast the generation of green energy in India for the years 2020 to 2023. The analysis shows that production of green energy will be increasing every year. While calculating linear regression confidence level of 95% is kept. Generation of green energy is a dependent variable. Chart 4 is prepared from the data in Table 3.

Chart 4

Forecasted Using Linear Regression

Table 4: Overall Forecasting Trends

Year	Investment Forecast (Billion US\$)	Green Energy Generation Forecast (in GwH)
2014	7	191025
2015	8.8	187158
2016	14.8	204182
2017	18.3	227973
2018	15.4	261797
2019	16.96F	294288
2020	18.02F	317035F
2021	19.08F	340760F
2022	20.13F	364484F
2023	21.19F	388209F

Chart 5

Table 5: Correlation Co-efficient of Investment & Generation of Green Energy

	Investment Forecast (Billion US\$)	Green Energy Generation Forecast (in GwH)
Investment Forecast (Billion US\$)	1	
Green Energy Generation Forecast (in GwH)	0.842451208	1

The correlation co-efficient of the investment made in green energy and the production of green energy in India is 0.842 which indicates a strong correlation between the independent and dependent variable. Here, the independent variable is investment and the dependent variable is the generation of green energy. Thus, more the investment made in green energy in India, it will lead to increase in the production in green energy.

Government Initiatives:

Some initiatives by the government of India to boost the Indian renewable sector are as follows:

- Rajasthan government has exempted solar energy from duty and there would be focus on utilizing solar power in agriculture and public health sectors in Budget 2019-20.
- New policy has been drafted for 2018-28 for growth of hydro projects in the country.
- The Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) has decided to provide custom and excise duty benefits to the solar rooftop sector, thus lowering the costs.
- The Indian Railways is taking increased efforts through sustained energy efficient measures and maximum use of clean fuel to cut down emission level by 33 per cent by 2030.

VI. Findings

The production of renewable energy in India constitutes 21.25% in 2019 whereas in 2014 it was 17.28% of the total power generation. Thus there is 4% increase in the generation of green energy. The predictive model of linear regression used to forecast the investments in green energy in India for the years 2019 to 2023 shows that the investments will be increasing every year. The analysis done to forecast the generation of green energy in India for the years 2019 to 2023 shows that production of green energy will be increasing every year. While calculating linear regression confidence level of 95% is kept.

VII. Conclusion

The correlation co-efficient of the investment made in green energy and the production of green energy in India is 0.842 which indicates a strong correlation between the independent and dependent variable. Here, the independent variable is investment and the dependent variable is the generation of green energy. Thus, more the investment made in green energy in India, it will lead to increase in the production in green energy.

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